

Integer sequence A327765

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The screen capture below shows an integer sequence accepted for publication by the OEIS in 2019; other contributors presented the sequence generating function (G.f.), formulas for general terms, and code to replicate the sequence in MAPLE and MATHEMATICA.

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(Greetings from [The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences!](#))

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A327765 a(n) is the trace of the n-th power of the 2 X 2 matrix [1 2; 3 4]. +40
1

2, 5, 29, 155, 833, 4475, 24041, 129155, 693857, 3727595, 20025689, 107583635, 577969553, 3105015035, 16681014281, 89615101475, 481437535937, 2586417882635, 13894964485049, 74647658190515, 401028219922673, 2154436415994395, 11574238519817321, 62180065431075395 ([list](#); [graph](#); [refs](#); [listen](#); [history](#); [text](#); [internal format](#))

OFFSET 0,1

LINKS Colin Barker, [Table of n, a\(n\) for n = 0..1000](#)
[Index entries for linear recurrences with constant coefficients](#), signature (5,2).

FORMULA a(n) = trace(M^n) where M is [1, 2; 3, 4].
From [Colin Barker](#), Sep 27 2019: (Start)
G.f.: (2 - 5*x) / (1 - 5*x - 2*x^2).
a(n) = 5*a(n-1) + 2*a(n-2) for n > 1.
a(n) = ((5-sqrt(33))/2)^n + ((5+sqrt(33))/2)^n.
(End)

MAPLE a:= n-> (<<0|1>, <2|5>>^n. <<2, 5>>)[1, 1]:
seq(a(n), n=0..23); # [Alois P. Heinz](#), Oct 07 2019

MATHEMATICA CoefficientList[Series[(2 - 5 x)/(1 - 5 x - 2 x^2), {x, 0, 22}], x] (*
[Michael De Vlieger](#), Sep 27 2019 *)
LinearRecurrence[{5, 2}, {2, 5}, 30] (* [Harvey P. Dale](#), Jun 25 2020 *)

PROG (PARI) a(n)={trace([1, 2; 3, 4]^n)} \\ [Andrew Howroyd](#), Sep 24 2019
(PARI) Vec((2 - 5*x) / (1 - 5*x - 2*x^2) + O(x^25)) \\ [Colin Barker](#), Sep 27 2019

CROSSREFS Cf. [A100638](#), [A124610](#), [A233020](#).

KEYWORD nonn,easy

AUTHOR [Adolf Cusmariu](#), Sep 24 2019

STATUS approved

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Last modified June 23 20:13 EDT 2023. Contains 363437 sequences. (Running on oeis4.)